

First suspected case: detection of an unknown pathogenic human coronavirus in post vaccination case

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Abstract: SARS CoV-2 is causing outbreaks in vaccinated and unvaccinated population. Till today, mutations are known to cause the new infections. This work is about a case of a person with vaccination history started showing typical coronaviral flu like symptoms. A number of real time tests for different pathogens like influenza A, B and C, respiratory syncytial virus A and B along with different SARS CoV-2, MERS and beta coronavirus are found negative. A conventional PCR test for pancoronavirus has shown specific bands in gel agarose, but real time PCR tests of other human coronaviruses like NL63, OC43, HKU1 and 229E were negative. These all indications lead to suspect that this is an unknown pathogenic coronavirus, therefore this is perhaps the first report to show that there is a presence of an unknown human coronavirus in this post vaccinated person as so-called breakthrough infection in a German city called Duisburg. It causes symptoms like coughing, running nose and scratchy sore throat. The proposed name of this unknown pathogenic human coronavirus is Bhatia coronavirus after the name of person, who discovered this.

Keywords: vaccine, breakthrough infection, SARS CoV-2, human corona virus, PCR test

Introduction: Pandemic SARS CoV-2 outbreaks are going on for last 2 years, since the reports from Chinese city Wuhan. ((Wu et al. 2020; Zhang et al. 2020; Zhu et al 2019) To contain this outbreak, there are a number of vaccines available around the world. (Livingston et al. 2021) Media is running a power PR campaign that each of us should get vaccinated. Millions of the people are vaccinated, but there are many outbreaks among vaccinated population so called breakthrough infections going on throughout the world. (Bergwerk et al. 2021; Kojima et al. 2021) Mutations are usually thought to be the main reason behind these breakthrough infections. Delta mutation is playing a key role to infect the vaccinated persons as available vaccines are developed on the data from wild strain, which was started causing outbreak in Jan. 2020. (Puowels et al. 2021)

Method: A vaccinated person (male) with Johnson and Johnson vaccination history in July, 2021 developed symptoms like coughing, itching in throat (needle pricking effect with pain) and running nose around the middle of Sept, 2021. At beginning, the symptoms were very light, but over the time of 2 weeks, the intensity of symptoms increased. The person gave the written consent for conducting and publication these studies.

Buccal swabs from deep throat areas were taken. RNA from two buccal swabs were isolated with mini column RNA isolation kit (Genekam, Germany). They were tested for presence of SARS CoV-2 with a real time PCR kit e.g., FR475 as this kit is in position to detect wild strain as well as most of mutations circulating SARS CoV-2 around the world in one step. Reference RNA SARS CoV-2 sample from NHS, UK was used as positive control. The real time PCR was conducted for beta coronavirus on the samples. Internal control for beta actin gene (FR799, Genekam, Germany) was used to confirm whether the successful isolation of RNA of both buccal swabs was done. After this, the RNA samples were tested for other respiratory viruses like influenza (A, B and C), respiratory syncytial virus A and B as well as parainfluenza 1,2 and 3 with real time PCR kits (Genekam, Germany). They all were negative. The samples were subjected to different human coronaviruses like OC43, NL63 and 229E real time PCR testing. At the end, a conventional pancoronavirus PCR test was used to detect the presence of coronaviruses with conventional thermocycler (Biometra, Germany). This test gave

positive results in 2% gel agarose (Roth, Germany). (Moes et al. 2005) To make sure that pancoronavirus PCR test is functioning properly, therefore minimum 4 different human coronavirus negative human RNA samples were run along with positive controls. Pancoronavirus test gave negative results with human RNA samples, but it gave positive results with positive controls too. All above said tests were repeated 3 times at least to make sure that the results are accurate. Two different real time machines ABI 7500 und QuantStudio5 (Thermofischer, USA) were used to test and reconfirm the results. The samples were tested with real time PCR test from WHO, which was negative too along with the testing of E gene specific real time PCR test to make sure that many different SARS CoV-2 specific real time PCR tests should be negative. Human coronavirus HKU1 was performed with negative results in real time settings. (Cui et al. 2011)

One more conventional PCR for detecting the different coronavirus test was carried. (Watanabe et al. 2010)

All real time PCR were conducted as following: 2 ul of isolated samples in each one step RNA PCR test was used. During the testing, the different dilutions between 1:0 to 1:1000 of the RNA samples were tested. Real time cycling conditions were 42 °C for 60 minutes, 70 °C for 10 minutes and 45 cycles of 90 °C for 15 seconds and 60 °C for 15 seconds.

Gene sequencing of PCR product from pancoronavirus test was carried with forward primer through an external service provider (Microsynth, Germany).

Results: The real time PCR results obtained are shown as different pictures. Picture 1 is showing the negative results about the tests for SARS CoV-2 for both samples, which were also negative for beta coronavirus assay. Picture 2 is showing that human internal control beta actin real time PCR was successful, hence it indicates that the both isolated samples contain RNA. A reference sample for SARS CoV-2 RNA gave successful positive result as shown in picture 4 in ABI7500 real time PCR thermocycler.

It was found that the samples were negative with real time PCR tests for different respiratory pathogens as shown in the table 1. Reconfirmation of SARS CoV-2 negative results was done through WHO nucleoprotein specific test. SARS CoV-2 specific test detected the reference strain as shown in picture 5. The RNA samples were run in different dilutions in real time PCR to make sure that there is no mistake or chance to miss the positive reactions, but these all dilutions were negative for SARS CoV-2, human coronaviruses as well as other respiratory pathogens tests.

Two different conventional PCR agarose gels are showing the pancoronavirus specific bands as seen in picture 3 in different dilutions. A point of the care test (Hotgen, China) was used at the beginning of the infection through the person himself, which was negative too.

The second conventional test conducted according Watanabe et al. was found negative.

Discussion: Till today the mutations as well as wild strains are thought to be causing breakthrough infections in vaccinated population. (Kasen et al. 2021) There are a number of PCR tests, which are being used to detect the presence of SARS CoV-2 samples. Such tests should be compared to find the best test for detection of SARS CoV-2. This comparison is avoided always. Why are regulatory agencies not comparing the approved and non-approved tests? This needs urgent discussion. Some comparison studies are being done with limited number of tests. (Uhteg et al. 2021). There is an urgent need to pinpoint which tests are in position to be used perfectly with wild strain and mutations. There are reports of validation of tests in literature, but there is no or very less indications, whether these tests can be used with detection of mutations too. (Chia et al. 2021; Degli-Angeli et al. 2020) The results in this work shows that WHO test may need to be improved and it needs to be compared for optimal performance with other tests as this is being done in the future studies. (Data not shown)

Moes et al. used first these wobble primers to discover human coronavirus NL63 circulating in Holland a few years ago and it is mentioned in their publication that these primers may lead to detect the presence of new coronavirus strains. (Vijgen et al.2008) This research work has perhaps led to detect again a new unknown strain coronavirus as 4 times the test was conducted in four different occasions in different dilutions and every time, the results were positive with bright bands at the same position. This strain needs to be sequenced and further characterized. The work is being done in this direction. These primers have been also successfully used in other studies to detect the human coronaviruses. (Cabeca et al, 2013; Silva et al. 2014)

Another conventional PCR to detect different members of coronavirus family was used, but the results were negative. It is known in the literature that this test is not position to detect wide of range of coronaviruses. (Watanabe et al. 2010; Holbrook et al. 2021)

This is perhaps the first publication suspecting that there may be unknown pathogenic human coronavirus strain causing breakthrough infections in vaccinated population with flu like symptoms, hence the tests needed to detect such cases should to be improved, so that one can have accurate information about the circulating pathogens to develop better therapeutic, preventive and monitoring options. Reference laboratories must have a large set of tests for respiratory pathogens detections because in this publication, a vast number of different tests are being used to find the cause of the illness. Such tests are commercially available and they are quite relatively affordable. Care must be taken while applying such commercial tests that the commercial identity has sufficient experience in virology to develop and manufacture pathogen specific tests. One of most important questions is to be addressed very urgently, which role is being played through this virus in progression of disease in vaccinated person with or without SARS CoV-2 and its mutations? Is this virus contributing to failure of therapy in patients as hidden infection today? Since how long is this virus circulating in population? What are consequences, if such patient left untreated?

Person tested told that he visited a bar after a few weeks getting vaccination, where he was without hygienic precautions particularly face mask. After that, he got this infection. It shows that it is important still for vaccinated population to take ordinary precautions like masks and social distancing too.

Direct sequencing of the PCR product may be difficult because the wobble primers are being used to detect a number of different coronaviruses, therefore sequencing was not successful, hence it may take some time to characterize this virus. External service provider warned about this risk of ailing before taking the order. The efforts are going to do sequencing using cloning method as well as next generation gene sequencing.

Human coronaviruses like OC43, NL63, 229E and HKU1 are known to cause the common cold cases, but SARS CoV-1, MERS and SARS CoV-2 can be causative agent of respiratory and digestive tract infections at the same time. Human coronaviruses like NL63 and 229E are alpha coronaviruses, but all other known infecting human beings like OC43, HKU1, SARS CoV-1, MERS, SARS CoV-2 are beta coronaviruses. These all-human infecting coronaviruses are originating from other animals like bats, rodents and camels. (Cui et al, 2019; Mann et al. 2020) In this research, the virus is detected from the human beings, therefore the question will be about the origin of this virus, whether it is originating too from animals or this is the first human coronavirus along human-to-human transmission because the person visited a beer bar?

The proposed name of this unknown virus from city Duisburg, Germany should be Bhatia coronavirus after the last name of the author, who discovered it. The given name will make it easier to do discussion about this virus in future. The main features of this virus today are it is negative in SARS CoV-2 specific tests, human coronaviruses like NL63, OC43, 229E and HKU1 along with the many of respiratory pathogens as listed in tables 1 and 2, but it is positive in conventional PCR test, where it shows specific band. WHO primers and probes for nucleoprotein gene, it is very important that user

should use linear mode during analysis of the real time results to see whether there is real increase in fluorescence taking place to judge the results. Still the user can face challenge to interpret the results with WHO test; hence it is advised that FR475 should be used, which give clear and reproducible results with SARS CoV-2.

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Picture 1 shows that the samples are negative for human coronavirus SARS CoV-2.

Picture 2 shows the results of internal controls indicate presence of human RNA in isolated samples.

Picture 3 shows 2 different gels with pancoronavirus specific band, which indicate the presence of the unknown virus in both RNA samples.

Picture 4 shows positive control with SARS CoV-2 Kit (FR475) in linear mode.

Picture 5 shows positive control with WHO test for nucleoprotein gene in linear mode.

Table 1: Results of pathogens tested with real time and conventional PCR methods.

	Pathogen (Source)	Result
1	SARS CoV-2 (FR475)	negative
2	Beta Coronavirus	negative
3	Influenza A	negative
4	Influenza B	negative
5	Influenza C	negative
6	Respiratory syncytial virus A	negative
7	Respiratory syncytial virus B	negative
8	Parainfluenza 1	negative
9	Parainfluenza 2	negative
10	Parainfluenza 3	negative
11	SARS CoV-2 (NP Gene, WHO)	negative
12	SARS CoV-2 (E Gene, WHO)	negative
13	Human Coronavirus NL63	negative
14	Human Coronavirus 229E	negative
15	Human Coronavirus OC43	negative
16	Human Coronavirus HK01	negative
17	MERS (Double Check)	negative
18	Coronavirus (Watanabe et al. 2010)	negative
19	Pancoronavirus	positive

Table 2 is showing minimum criteria to define this unknown coronavirus.

	Pathogen (Source)	Result
1	SARS CoV-2 (FR475)	negative
2	Beta Coronavirus	negative
3	SARS CoV-2 (NP Gene, WHO)	negative
4	SARS CoV-2 (E Gene, WHO)	negative
5	Human Coronavirus NL63	negative
6	Human Coronavirus 229E	negative
7	Human Coronavirus OC43	negative
8	Human Coronavirus HK01	negative
9	MERS (Double Check)	negative
10	Pancoronavirus (Moes et al.)	positive

